

Speciation of green iron nanoparticles *in situ* by a simple UV-Visible technique

Kesarla Mohan Kumar and Badal Kumar Mandal*

Trace Elements Speciation Research Laboratory, Environmental and Analytical Chemistry Division,
School of Advanced Sciences, VIT University, Vellore-633 014, Tamilnadu, India

E-mail : badalmandal@vit.ac.in; badalkmandal@gmail.com

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Abstract : In order to develop green manufacturing processes for nanomaterials, plants extracts are used to synthesize the nanoparticles in present days. In this context, synthesizing iron nanoparticles using plant extract was developing from past few years since metallic iron nanoparticles was known for its wide variety of applications. But the preliminary characterization techniques like UV-Visible spectroscopy and Powder XRD do not give the necessary information on the type of iron nanoparticles present in green iron colloids which needs expensive Mossbauer spectroscopy, Raman spectroscopy, Electron Energy Loss Spectroscopy (EELS) in the transmission electron microscope (TEM) and X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS) study. So, the present study has developed a simple UV-Visible based spectrophotometric technique where baseline correction plays an important role in characterizing the type of nanoparticles present in green iron colloids synthesized by plant extract. This was the novelty of the present technique which has made an easiest tool to speciate green nZVI without using costly microscopic techniques from iron oxide nanoparticles. Phenolic rich *Terminalia chebula* aqueous extract was used for reduction of iron salt.

Keywords : UV-Vis technique, speciation, green iron colloids, *Terminalia chebula*.

Introduction

The unique optoelectronic and physiochemical properties make metallic nanoparticles (NPs) ease for different applications such as environmental remediation¹, biosensing², optics³, media recording⁴ and catalysis⁵. Metallic NPs of desired size and shapes can be synthesized readily using physical and chemical methods⁶. But, these methods involve reducing agents, non biodegradable stabilizing/capping agents or organic solvents which are toxic and therefore potentially dangerous to both biological systems and environment. Moreover, most of these methods demand convoluted controls or abnormal conditions making them quite expensive and complicate.

Recently, many researchers were interested in using green chemistry principles to synthesize metal NPs. The biosynthesis of NPs has been attracted tremendous interest due to their cost effective, eco-friendliness and a best alternative to traditional chemical and physical methods. As a result, nanomaterials have been synthesized using microorganisms^{7,8} and plant extracts⁹⁻¹². Synthesis of NPs using plant extracts is more advantageous due to easy scale up over microorganisms which involve biohazards

and intricate process in maintaining cell cultures⁹. Identifying environmental friendly materials which are multifunctional is very important in this area. For example, green tea polyphenol acts both as reducing and capping agents for the synthesis of Ag and Pd NPs⁹⁻¹².

Among metal NPs, iron NPs have been considered very important because of its wide applications in environmental remediation¹ and catalysis⁵. But synthesizing iron NPs, especially zero valent iron NPs (nZVI) require inert atmosphere to protect aerial oxidation which in turn makes the process expensive. The biosynthesis was well established in the case of noble metals such as Ag, Au and palladium. Only a few bio-based reports were available for the synthesis of iron NPs¹⁰⁻¹². After critical evaluation of the recent articles published on iron NPs¹⁰⁻¹², we noticed from our experiments and also published literature that preliminary characterization techniques like UV-Vis, XRD do not provide enough information to judge the type of iron NPs formed except Mossbauer spectroscopy, Raman spectroscopy, Electron Energy Loss Spectroscopy (EELS) in the transmission electron microscope (TEM) and X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS) study.

The present study has tried to develop a simple analytical method to address this problem and synthesized iron NPs using aqueous extract of phenolic rich *Terminalia chebula* (*T. chebula*) which is used widely in Indian Ayurvedic medicine. We have developed a simple UV-Vis technique where baseline correction plays an important role in analysing the type of nanoparticles present in green iron colloids.

Results and discussion

UV-Vis study :

UV-Vis spectra of green iron NPs are shown in Figs. 1 and 2. Two different UV-Vis studies were conducted in order to check the status of iron NPs (whether nZVI or iron oxide NPs) by green method (i) using water for baseline correction (Fig. 1) and (ii) using *T. chebula* aqueous extract for baseline correction (Fig. 2). Using extract

Fig. 1. UV-Visible spectra of iron NPs obtained from three different extracts (a) 2% (w/v), (b) 3% and (c) 4% where water was used for baseline correction.

Fig. 2. UV-Visible spectra of iron NPs obtained from three different extracts (a) 2% (w/v), (b) 3% and (c) 4% where respective extracts were used for baseline correction.

for baseline correction, it is possible to monitor simultaneously the formation of nZVI, complex formation with excess polyphenols present in *T. chebula* extract and afterwards formation of iron oxide NPs *in situ*. The UV-Vis spectra of iron NPs synthesized using *T. chebula* aqueous extract showed continuous absorption in the visible range with a broad peak at 575 nm, when UV-Vis spectrum was recorded with water as blank. Nadagouda *et al.*¹¹ obtained similar UV-Vis spectra for amorphous iron NPs synthesized using aqueous tea extract, but no broad peak appeared at 575 nm. Normally the absorption spectrum depends on various factors such as particle size, shape, and the refractive index of the surrounding media¹³.

In the current work, we performed UV-Vis study of iron NPs using *T. chebula* aqueous extract which was used in the synthesis, was used for baseline correction. In

this case three bands appeared at around 340 nm, 405 nm and a broad peak at 583 nm respectively whereas a sharp peak at 216 nm appeared when aqueous solution of ferrous sulphate was tested against water as blank (data not shown). The absorption at 340 nm is indicative of formation of nZVI¹⁴, the absorption at 583 nm clears the formation of iron oxide NPs^{13,14} and the absorption at 405 nm may be due to the interaction of metallic iron with excessive polyphenols present in the extract. Initially UV-Vis study of iron NPs was done with water as baseline corrector (Fig. 1). No peak was appeared in UV region. Hence all previous reports did not distinguish between iron oxide NPs and nZVI¹⁰⁻¹².

Further, UV-Vis spectra of chemically synthesized nZVI, nZVI + glucose and nZVI + gallic acid are shown in Figs. S1, S2 and S3 respectively (as supporting information). UV-Vis spectra of chemically synthesized nZVI

Fig. S1. UV-Vis spectrum of synthesised nZVI by chemical method. S2. UV-Vis spectrum of the product obtained by interacting 10 mg of nZVI with 10 mL of 1% glucose. Inset shows UV-Vis spectrum of glucose. S3. UV-Vis spectrum of the product obtained by interacting 10 mg of nZVI with 10 mL of 1% of gallic acid. Inset shows UV-Vis spectrum of gallic acid. S4. EDS spectrum of iron nanoparticles obtained by green method.

showed absorption maximum at 343 nm (Fig. S1, supporting information) which is similar to the peak that appeared at 340 nm for nZVI synthesized using *T. chebula* aqueous extract (Fig. 2). In order to characterize the source of the peak at 400 nm the following experiment was carried out. 10 mg of chemically synthesized nZVI was interacted with 10 mL 1% glucose solution and the UV-Vis spectra showed a broad absorption peak at around 400 nm (Fig. S2, supporting information) which is similar to the peak that appeared at 400 nm when *T. chebula* aqueous extract was used as baseline corrector (Fig. 2). Glucose is one of the hydrolyzed products present in *T. chebula* aqueous extract and hence it was taken for interaction study with iron NPs. The polyphenols present in the form of tannin i.e. galloyl glucose in *T. chebula* easily hydrolyses to glucose and gallic acid under very mild condition. On the other hand it is very clear that interaction between gallic acid and nZVI (Fig. S3, supporting information) results the formation of iron oxide¹³. From the above observations it is very clear that the formation of nZVI took place in the green method. Also, nZVI spontaneously reacted with air or water to form iron-iron oxide core shell NPs^{15,16}. But in the present situation, the excess polyphenols present in *T. chebula* aqueous extract interacted with nZVI formed during green synthesis and favored the formation of iron oxide NPs. Results of UV-Vis study strongly confirmed this findings (Fig. 2).

To establish the above assumption the effect of increasing concentration of *T. chebula* aqueous extract on nZVI was studied (Fig. 2). The result shows that the intensity of peak due to nZVI decreased inversely with the concentration of *T. chebula* aqueous extract. This is because more polyphenols were available to interact with nZVI favoring the formation of iron oxide NPs. Because the intensity of the peak at 583 nm increased simultaneously, this confirmed the formation of iron oxide NPs in the expense of nZVI.

When water was used for baseline correction, the signals at the UV-region didn't appear due to the interference effects from traces of compounds present in the resultant product obtained by interacting *T. chebula* extract with $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The signal of nZVI didn't appear due to interference of phytochemicals present in the resultant reaction mixture. In order to separate the true spectro-

scopic signals from interference effects or to remove background effects due to stains or traces of compounds, a selective pre-processing technique (baseline correction) using appropriate concentrations of extract was used which eased the characterization of green iron nanocolloids in a simple way. This was the novelty of the present technique which has made an easiest tool to characterize nZVI during green iron synthesis without using costly microscopic techniques.

Crystallographic study :

The XRD pattern of iron NPs was shown in Fig. 3. The pattern lacks distinct diffraction peak, suggesting that iron NPs are amorphous. In the XRD pattern of iron nanoparticle a broad peak was present at about $2\theta = 25^\circ$, which can be attributed to interaction of nZVI with excess polyphenols present in *T. chebula* aqueous extract.

Fig. 3. XRD pattern of iron NPs synthesized by green method.

Similar type of poor crystalline XRD pattern was observed for iron-oleate complex¹⁷ and iron NPs synthesized using sorghum bran extract¹⁸. The powder XRD pattern of iron NPs did not have discrete diffraction peaks which are symptomatic and the synthesized iron NPs were amorphous in nature. Njagi *et al.*¹⁸ obtained similar pattern to amorphous iron NPs synthesized using aqueous sorghum barn extract.

Morphology of iron NPs :

The SEM image of iron NPs (Fig. 4a) suggests that the iron NPs agglomerated to form irregular clusters. The average diameter of the iron NPs calculated from TEM micrographs were in the range of 25–50 nm (Fig.

4b). Nadagouda *et al.*^{10,11} synthesized iron NPs of different sizes and morphologies using aqueous tea extract. The sizes and morphologies of the synthesized iron NPs were dependent on the concentration of the extract.

Fig. 4. (a) SEM image of iron NPs, (b) TEM image of iron NPs synthesized by green method.

Elemental analysis :

Fig. S4 (supplementary data) shows a representative EDS spectrum of iron NPs. The iron NPs were primarily composed of iron. The appearance of oxygen peak suggests either the surface oxidation of nZVI or iron oxide formation. Elemental analysis using EDS detected the presence of oxygen in the synthesized iron NPs. nZVI are very sensitive and often react spontaneously upon exposure to air or water forming iron-iron oxide core-shell NPs^{15,16}. Even the formation of nZVI took place, gallic acid and glucose moieties present in the extract reacted further with nZVI which leads to the formation of iron oxide NPs. The EDS results also revealed exclusively the presence of iron and oxygen which indicates the synthesized NPs were essentially pure.

Iron NPs are widely used in waste water treatment and environmental remediation. In aquatic environments, these NPs aggregate easily leading to rapid sedimentation and impair mobility. Non stabilized iron NPs can settle out easily at less than 10 min. However, no sedimentation was observed visually even after a month of storage in the present study (Data not shown). This observation suggests that the phenolic compounds present in the *T. chebula* extract help in stabilizing the iron NPs. This level of stabilization is very useful in environmental remediation and some catalytic applications where preventing the aggregation are very important.

Experimental

Materials and chemicals :

Ferrous sulphate heptahydrate ($\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$,

Qualigens, 98%) and sodium borohydrate (NaBH_4 , sdFine Chem Limited, 98%) were used for the preparation of iron NPs. All aqueous solutions were made using deionized water (DW), *Terminalia chebula* were purchased from local market. *Terminalia chebula* extracts were rich in polyphenols and other reductive bio-molecules containing multiple hydroxyl groups such as corilagin and di/tri-galloyl glucose in high levels. These phenolic compounds have reduction potential ranging from 0.3 to 0.6 V and are mainly responsible for bio-reduction of metal ions and stabilization of resultant NPs.

Synthesis of zero valent iron NPs (nZVI) by chemical method :

Zero Valent Iron NPs (nZVI) were synthesized chemically as per our patented procedure^{19,20}.

Synthesis of iron NPs using green method :

T. chebula seed was grinded to fine powder after drying and the aqueous extract was prepared with DW at 90 °C using a temperature controlled water bath. Three different extracts were prepared i.e. (a) 2 g, (b) 3 g and (c) 4 g of *T. chebula* powder boiled in 100 ml of DW. pH of the aqueous *T. chebula* extracts were 3.59, 3.42 and 3.29 respectively.

Iron NPs were prepared by adding 2 mL of 0.01 M FeSO_4 to 10 mL of three different *T. chebula* extracts (at ambient temperature). The mixture was shaken thoroughly for a minute and allowed to stand for 1 h.

Characterization of iron NPs :

The UV-Vis absorption spectra were obtained using a Jasco V-670 UV-Vis spectrophotometer. Morphological studies were carried out using Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) and High Resolution Transmission Electron Microscope (HR-TEM). SEM coupled with Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (SEM/EDS) analysis was done using a Carl Zeiss SEM Instrument attached to EVO MA 15 (Oxford Instrument). The solid samples were sprinkled on the adhesive carbon tape which was supported on the metallic disk and images were taken. Simultaneously, elemental analysis was done using EDS. Particle size of iron NPs were determined by using TEM (Philips Tecnai-12, FEI, Netherlands) operating at an accelerated voltage of 200 kV. Sampling was done by dispersing sample using ultrasonic bath and a drop of the dispersion was applied on Holey Carbon TEM supported grid (Ernest Fullam,

Inc., Latham, NY). Powder XRD analysis was done using Bruker D8 Advance Diffractometer (Bruker AXS, Germany) with Cu K α radiation ($\lambda = 1.54 \text{ \AA}$). XRD pattern of nZVI samples was recorded over a 2-theta range of 10–90°. The instrument was calibrated using LaB6 prior to the experiment.

Conclusions :

A simple UV-Vis spectrophotometric method was developed by selective pre-processing technique using plant extract of appropriate concentration used for the synthesis of green iron nanocolloids. The formation of nZVI during the green synthesis is confirmed without using costly microscopic techniques. Although the formation of nZVI occurred during the synthesis the interaction between nZVI and the excess oxidized polyphenols present in the aqueous medium favoured the formation of iron oxide NPs. There may be possibilities to achieve nZVI selectively using non-aqueous solvent systems under the controlled volume of *T. chebula* extract. EDS also reveals that the iron NPs formed were essentially pure which makes them potentially useful in biological applications.

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